

Letter from Bernard Collinson on the Opening of the Great Exhibition

London, 1 May 1851

Transcribed and edited by **Elonka Dunin**, 2025

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Source

Original manuscript: Private correspondence of the Collinson family, 1845–1852 (Manuscript) (CLS/48/2), Collinson Papers, Caird Library & Archive, National Maritime Museum, Greenwich, UK.

Description

A private letter from Thomas Bernard Collinson (1811–1883) to his mother Amelia Collinson, describing in detail the preparations for and opening ceremony of the Great Exhibition at the Crystal Palace, Hyde Park, London, 1 May 1851.

Citation

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Transcript

My dear Mother – you must come back again - you have seen nothing - the Crystal Palace of April 30 with its half-painted columns, its half-laid floor, its hoops of workmen, its empty boxes, its straw and rubbish, & carts, its hammers and noise, was a thing we all saw & knew & understood. The Crystal Palace of May 1st was another building altogether & was built & finished between 3 a.m. on Wednesday and 6 a.m. on Thursday by the fairy gnomes, I suppose for I know not how or when human labourers could have done it.

What the Crystal Palace was on Wednesday morning you can form an idea - the whole space was crowded with workmen & strewed with straw and empty boxes, things were still unpacking. The contractors in thousands were at work finishing their painting, mending the

floor, repairing the roof, fitting the counters, Exhibitors were thronging to do what they could to the last moment, & hundreds were besieging the gate outside, whom the Executive committee would not allow even a last chance. Carts were still arriving and the whole exterior a chaos of empty boxes through which only a faint outline of order could be discerned.

Down the centre the canvas enclosures of the great objects blocked up the view, plants were in every direction, and seats for the multitude running up on all sides. At 2 o'clock p.m. according to the usual sudden despotism of the Executive a great bell was rung in the building & 200 of the foot guards were drawn up in 2 lines in the transept and marching East & West drove every one before them out of the building, which act of military despotism was exercised I will say with great forbearance.

The contractors then began to work in earnest. They had to clear out the rubbish, erect the Royal platform and canopy, lay the matting, put up the seats, clear to mouths of the entrances, and hoist the flap. And be it remembered that to the last moment it was thought doubtful by the public if it would be ready. A month ago it was thought improbable by everybody. The foreigners so reckoned upon the postponement, that they took it easy. They did not know, nobody knew, least of all the British workmen themselves, what they can do when put upon their mettle. And it has been this mettle, this feeling, that they were the centre of attraction of the world, that has made every individual of us work to his full stretch, and has produced these fairy-like transformations, & it is such quick works as these that best show the great power of the independent spirit of the Englishman.

Ancient labors have moved their mighty blocks and excavated their temples, and reared pyramids but I do think it required free beefeating Englishmen to create in 6 months a palace of 8 Acres and to fill it with statues & fountains & trees - and production of every climate & machines and manufactures of every use.

On Wednesday night at ½ past 2 a.m. I left the disorderly Crystal Palace and by Thursday morning at ½ past 5 a.m. I walked into a new Crystal Palace - clean and furnished. In the centre the Crystal Fountain playing, as wonderful and as high as any shopkeeper could wish, round it was a platform of red cloth with a raised red platform on the North side - suspended over it a large blue and red canopy - the rest of the transept filled with statues & fountains. Down the vista of the central avenue on either hand was to us the most marvelous of all - a clear unbroken walk laid with matting & studded all down on the British side, with pyramids of damask, huge columns with block of alum, clocks, domes, mirrors, each on its crimson pedestal, and on the Foreign side with an army of statues & the Koh-i-Noor [diamond] in its golden cage - & all fitted with rows of crimson seats. Up the galleries the railing was all lined with crimson - from each bay was hung a red & white [banner with] the name of its kind & nation, & in every bay a carpet. The glass chandeliers in the galleries glittered in the sun & at the East end could be seen the American Eagle with United States in huge letters. The most conspicuous of any nation with the least show above over the roof, the yellow calico gave a hazy shade to the whole & through the glass could be seen on every pinnacle of the long long parapet the banner of some British town or foreign nation.

All much beyond any picture that has ever been drawn of it. But this beautiful emptiness was to be closely filled with a choice collection of British produce such as no Executive could collect & Owen Jones could not paint.

At ½ past 5 a.m. I passed the Albert gate & carriages of ladies stood waiting for its opening at ½ past 9 a.m. Some imaginative policeman said the line extended to Lincolns Inn Fields (3 miles away), and I stood some time at the South entrance watching the incessant flow of ladies from the carriages, all in Summer dresses & each more beautiful than the last, and as I walked down the double avenue in the transept of the Belles of London sealed in close rank from one end to the other of the whole length, I was proud to see, that if the Foreigners surpass us in Fine arts, we had enough specimens of native produce to match all the statues that were ever chiseled since the days of Phidias.

By 11 o'clock a.m. all the avenue below & every gallery above was alive with all the rank of England. About this time various little episodes occurred, disputes about seats, abuse of *soi-disant* gentlemen (French for "self-styled"), who would not make way for ladies & with considerable difficulty the sappers & police cleared the crimson square round the fountain in the center & let the fierce-looking gentlemen at arms environ the throne, backed by the biggest beefeaters that ever wore the Elizabethan costume. Then the Square became filled again with foreign functionaries in every colour & make of uniform, & Royal commissioners in Court costume, of all of which the gaudy Spaniard was the ugliest & the blue & red Dane perfectly plain, the handsomest. [Abbott] Lawrence, the American Minister was one of the finest looking men. Sir Charles Napier (naval hero from Trafalgar) then arrived & was cheered the whole way, he looked better & younger than I expected. Then there was a great cheer in the transept & the Duke (of Wellington, hero of Waterloo) walked slowly into the Square – the only soldier in white trousers. He looked well pleased & lively & sat down by the Marquess of Anglesey (Henry Paget, cavalry commander from Waterloo) – at which there was renewed cheering. Then Lord John Russell (Prime Minister) hopped past without notice. Then the great Mandarin in costume made himself quite at home in the circle, which considering he is about as much a Mandarin as my boy Alphonso, was a piece of impudence which none but a Chinaman could have done. Then there was a flourish of trumpets & presently a roar of cheers from the transept & the Queen & Prince Albert & the children walked past from the North side to the throne, preceded by blue & gold officers of state & followed by the Prince of Prussia & a long train of great personages. The Queen sat in her chair or throne & the Prince stood on her left looking as happy as possible, & the children on each side. Behind were Princess Mary of Cambridge & the Duke (of Cambridge, son of George III and father of Mary), who is getting like his father & the Duchess of Sutherland, who was better dressed than the Queen, but too bold to be Queen-like, & several ladies in white & among the trees the Royal people in state liveries.

At this time the scene in the centre was so gorgeous as to throw the rest of the Crystal Palace into shade & I suspect the Royal commissioners were as much astonished as Alladin when he first rubbed his lamp. The fresh green leaves of the trees was quite a relief to the eye. The mighty chorus of Exeter Hall was almost lost in this great building. It could not be heard beyond the transept.

Then the Court and commissioners crowded round the Throne which was so low I was obliged to go close up to her Majesty's Ministers to get a sight of her. Then there was a dead silence, I thought galleries would give way from the pressing of the people to hear the Queen speak. Colonel (William) Reid said he thought it was one of the most impressive speeches he ever heard. Then the old archbishop stood forward in his canonicals & repeated a prayer, the Queen & Prince paying great attention. Immediately after burst forth the Hallelujah chorus – which was the grandest thing of the day & sounded like a fitting song of triumph for such a building & the procession moved the whole central avenue from end to end. First Mr. Paxton (Joseph Paxton, designer of the Crystal Palace) in a court dress – then Mr. Digby Wyatt (Matthew Digby Wyatt, the Exhibition's Art Secretary) – then the Executive & British & Foreign Officers, the Royal Commissioners of whom Lord Overstone (banker and philanthropist) was the finest looking, then the Foreign minister & Ambassadors & the Chinese Mandarin where ever he could find a place. The Duke & Lord Anglesey helping each other along, the people taking up the cheering as they went along – but we in the transept could hardly hear the cheers at the end – much less the organs – when they got back to the Throne. The poor Lord Chamberlain rather done up considering he has walked $\frac{3}{4}$ of a mile backwards – he mustered up breath to declare by the Queen's command the Exhibition was opened, at which there was a flourish of trumpets & the Royal party retired, & in two minutes the transept was a mass of people trying to go different ways. It has already become the Great Lounge of London & everybody is astonished at it, none more so than those who aspired to make it. If you only sit still in the Transept - you meet everybody in London, are alternately confused by perpetual new pieces of art, & transfixed by perpetual new beauties.

T. B. Collinson

The Exhibition continued open from May till November & closed with nearly the same ceremonies.

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